

Comparison of Cheiloscopy Patterns in Twins Residing in a City of North Maharashtra- A Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Within forensic odontology, cheiloscropy provides a minimally intrusive supplement to techniques like dactyloscopy by analysing distinctive lip print patterns for human identification. Similar to fingerprints, lip prints exhibit individual heterogeneity and stability, although research on twins is still scarce despite evidence of genetic implications. In order to evaluate forensic value, quadrant-specific matching, and genetic similarity, this cross-sectional study analysed cheiloscopy patterns in twins from North Maharashtra. **Methods:** Twins (n=25 pairs) were recruited from an OPD at the dental institution and local Gynecologist database. (March-November 2025). After ethical approval written informed consent per Declaration of Helsinki, lip prints were collected and imprinted on paper. Data analysed via Chi-square, unpaired t-test. **Results:** Of 25 twin pairs, 83.3% showed overall similar patterns ($\chi^2=12.09$, $p=0.0005$); 72% matched across all quadrants ($p<0.028$). Pattern distribution: Type I (28%), II (26%), III (18%), I' (14%), IV (12%), V (2%), with quadrant variations (e.g., Type I highest in third quadrant at 8.87%). **Conclusion:** Twin lip prints exhibit strong genetic similarity (83.3% overall) with quadrant-specific variations (28% unmatched), supporting cheiloscropy's forensic value for individualization, even among genetically similar individuals.

Keywords: Cheiloscropy; lip prints; twins; Suzuki-Tsuchihashi classification; forensic odontology.

INTRODUCTION:

Cheiloscropy registers and classifies the human lip transition zone, located between the inner mucosa and lip skin.^[1] The term "cheiloscropy" comes from "cheilos," which means lips, and "scopy," which means to look. This is the way for identifying a person. Since ancient times, identification has played a vital and significant part in forensic medicine. There are numerous conventional techniques for personal identification, such as anthropometry, dactylography, sex determination, blood group differentiation, DNA profiling, odontology, etc; Venkatesh R et al (2011).^[2,3] It serves as an adjuvant method. Cheiloscropy is an accessible and minimally invasive research tool. Because of its permanence and distinctiveness, like fingerprints, cheiloscropy is a rapidly developing technology for human identification in this genre.^[4-6] As a source of tactical and criminalistic information, lip prints can be utilized in crime detection tasks in addition to identification and evidential purposes; Thete SG et al (2024). Conclusions about the nature of the incident, the number of participants, sexes, cosmetics used, habits,

occupational characteristics, and the pathological alterations of the lips themselves can all be drawn from a lip print found at the crime scene.^[7] Lip prints can be discovered on various surfaces, including glass, clothing, and silverware. The vermilion border of the lips contains tiny salivary and sebaceous glands, which, together with the tongue's moisturizing action, increases the probability of latent lip prints. As a result, when looking for lip prints, it is always important to consider the possibility of latent prints Kumar P et al.^[8] Identical twins are more unique to cheiloscropy than non-identical twins.^[9] Amongst the different studies done on lip prints in the past, those done on twins are rather few and remain an area of research with voids. The research of lip prints pattern in twins would make a significant contribution, as earlier studies have shown that uniovular twins share the same proteins and genetic information but have different finger prints Sugatha M et al (2022).^[10] Thus, any significant changes in lip print patterns would be extremely important in the realm of forensic medicine. Also, there is limited literature on the use of herbal lip products in cheiloscropy, highlighting

the need for studies evaluating their effectiveness. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to use herbal lip tint in a cheiloscopy study and find its use in field of forensic odontology.

Rationale of Study- Literature in the past indicated that the patterns of lip is strongly influenced by hereditary characteristics. Previous studies comparing twin lip prints have revealed some degree of resemblance in cheiloscopic patterns, particularly main groove patterns. Previous researches have shown that twins share the same proteins and genetic information but have different fingerprints. Comparing lip patterns between twins is equally important *Debta FM et al* (2018).⁽¹¹⁾ Significant major similarities or differences discovered in twin lip print patterns will greatly benefit the field of forensic medicine. The aim of this study was comparison of cheiloscopic patterns in twins residing in a city of North Maharashtra.

Study design:

- The study followed the design of a cross-sectional study and data from March 2025 to Nov of 2025. The study was conducted in Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology in a dental institution located in city of Maharashtra.
- The data was collected from twins visiting in outpatient department (OPD) of the institution and database from local gynaecologist hospital in city of North Maharashtra region.
- The research was performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki principles.

Ethical Consideration:

- Data collection and respective analysis was approved by the Research Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC). (MGV/KBHDC/IEC80/2024-2025).

Patient Consent:

- Written informed consent was taken from all the patients explaining the procedure of the study.

Eligibility criteria:

A. INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Twins willing to participate in study.

B. EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Patients with pathological disorders in lip like cleft lip, scarring of lips, etc.
- Patient with h/o trauma/ surgery in lip region.
- Patient allergic to applicator like lip tint/ink.
- Patient with piercings, cuts, burns, active herpetic lesions, or any type of raised lesion that distorts groove patterns on their lips, had not had an adverse or allergic reaction to facial cosmetics, cleansers, or adhesive tape.

Primary Objectives

- 1.To determine cheiloscopic patterns in twins as per Suzuki and Tsuchihashi Classification.
2. To compare cheiloscopic patterns among the twins using the same classification in the city of North Maharashtra.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Sample size calculating formula:

$$N=2\frac{S^2(Z1+Z2)^2}{(M1-M2)^2}$$

- The samples were divided by using simple random sampling technique.
- Among the materials used were sterilised cotton, mild lip cleanser, an herbal maroon-coloured ^[12] [Just Herbs- Enriched Lip tint (Just Herbs)], white bond paper (size- 15×15 cm), a disposable lip applicator. Due to its biocompatibility, a lower probability of allergic responses, and higher participant acceptability than traditional synthetic lip cosmetics, an herbal lip tint was chosen to record lip prints. **[Figure.1]**

Fig.1 Materials

- Each individual of a twin pair, lip print was captured after verbal agreement was obtained. The participants were instructed to sit comfortably on the dental chair and maintain a relaxed lips position. Before recording lip prints, the lips were cleaned with mild lip cleanser for debridement of any debris on the superficial grooves of lips.
- To create distinct and repeatable lip print patterns, participants' lips were consistently covered with a standardized dark matte lip tint using a lip applicator. A fresh lip tint and disposable lip applicators were used every time for lip print recording to avoid cross infection.
- The white bond paper of size- (15×15 cm) was carefully placed on participants lip and then very little pressure was applied to make the lip impression. The pressure was applied from one direction only so that, lip prints have maximum superficial cheiloscopy prints recording. At the end the lips were cleaned by sterilised cotton. [Figure.2.]

Fig.2. Photograph of cheiloscopy lip impressions of a twin pair on a bond paper

- All the lip impression photographs were taken using a digital camera. The photographic lip impressions were then transferred to MS paint. The lines were drawn using drawing tools to divide lip prints in quadrants.
- In this study a four-compartment method was used. The lips were divided into four quadrants and allotted the digits 1-4 in a clockwise direction starting from upper right corner of the lip. The upper lip was divided into right upper quadrant (UR) and left upper quadrant (UL) and the lower lip was divided into right lower quadrant (LR) and left lower quadrant (LL). For each quadrant the lip pattern was recorded as per Suzuki and Tsuchihashi classification in each individual. Then comparison of cheiloscopy patterns was made in between twin pair as per Suzuki and Tsuchihashi Classification and data was then collected. [Figure.3.]

Fig.3. Evaluation of cheiloscopy patterns in lip print photographic record in all quadrants.

Classification of Suzuki and Tsuchihashi (1971)^[13] was applied in the study:

- TYPE I - A clear-cut groove running vertically across the lip.
- TYPE I' - Partial length groove of Type I.
- TYPE II- A branched groove.
- TYPE III- An intersected groove.
- TYPE IV- A reticular groove.
- TYPE V- Unidentified or other patterns.

Data Management and Analysis Procedure

- Type of data was continuous quantitative.
- It included the various tables, graphical representation and statistical tests to achieve aims and objective of the study.
- The data obtained was coded and entered into (Microsoft Excel Worksheet. XII).

Statistical Analysis:

- A power analysis was conducted using G*Power version 3.0.1 (Franz Faul, Universität Kiel, Germany).
- The data was analysed by using post hoc test and other appropriate statistical techniques with the help of statistical software; Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 17.0 version.
- An unpaired t test was used to compare the quantitative study parameters between groups, whilst the Chi square test was used to compare the qualitative study parameters.

RESULTS:

Our study used a total determined sample size of 25 twin pairs. A comprehensive analysis of cheiloscopy pattern comparisons across 25 pairs of twins, encompassing both comparable and dissimilar results was observed in our study. In relation to forensic personality evaluations, it assessed overall pattern concordance was observed. The chi-square test ($\chi^2=12.09$, $p = 0.0005$) revealed that (83.3) percent of twin pairs had similar lip print patterns. The dissimilarity rate of 16.7% (4 pairs) indicates that distinct variances may be caused by environmental or developmental variables [Table 1] & [Fig.4.]. Overall similarity was however higher than quadrant-specific matching in related analyses.^[10]

Table 1: Comparison of similarity/dissimilarity of cheiloscopy patterns between twins

	Frequency (n=25)	Percentage (%)	Statistical Analysis	P value, Significance
Similar	21/25	83.3%	Chi-square = 12.09	p = 0.0005* (Statistically significant)
Dissimilar	4/25	16.7%		

**Statistically highly significant; ** denotes significance

Fig.4. Similarity/dissimilarity of cheiloscopy patterns between twins

[Table 2] analyses the cheiloscopy patterns of 25 pairs of twins in each of the four lip quadrants (upper left, upper right, lower left, lower right). By evaluating quadrant-specific concordance, which can be essential for forensic applications where exact pattern alignment matters, it expands on overall similarity. Of the 25 twin pairs, 72% showed matched lip print patterns across all quadrants, while 28% had mismatches in at least one quadrant. [Fig.5.] The significant p-value ($p < 0.028$) from the chi-square test supports non-random matching, underscoring genetic influence on lip print formation.

Table 2: Comparison of lip prints between of cheiloscopy patterns of twins for matching in all the quadrants

	Frequency (n=25)	Percentage (%)
Matched	18/25	72%
Unmatched	7/25	28%
P = 4.84, $p < 0.028^{**}$		

Statistical Analysis: $P = 4.84$, $p < 0.028^{**}$ (statistically significant, typically at $p < 0.05$ level; $**$ denotes significance).

Fig.5. Comparison of image between images of cheiloscopy patterns of twins for matching in all the quadrants

[Table 3] provides descriptive statistics on the frequency of six cheiloscopy (lip print) pattern types observed among study subjects (likely the 25 twin pairs, $n=50$ lips total) across all four lip quadrants (upper left, upper right, lower left, lower right). Patterns are classified per standard nomenclature: Type I (straight line), Type I' (slightly curved), Type II (curved with bifurcations), Type III (intersected lines), Type IV (reticular/net-like), and Type V (irregular). Straight and curved patterns dominate (Type I: 28%, Type II: 26%), comprising over half of observations, while complex (Type III/IV) and irregular (Type V) patterns are less common.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of cheiloscopy pattern type among study subjects in all the quadrants

cheiloscopy pattern types according to Suzuki and Tsuchihashi Classification	Percentage (%)
Type I	28%
Type I'	14%
Type II	26%
Type III	18%
Type IV	12%
Type V	2%

DISCUSSION:

Cheiloscopy is becoming increasingly popular as an auxiliary forensic identification tool due to its distinctiveness, relative permanence, and ease of recording lip print patterns. The results of our study provide important data for comprehending the personal and inherited nature of lip prints, especially in twins.

In our study, 83.3% of twin pairs showed general similarity in cheiloscopy patterns, whereas 16.7% revealed differing patterns, a discrepancy that was deemed statistically significant ($p = 0.0005$) showing strong genetic effect. The results of our study, align with those of Fernandes *et al.* (2017), who observed significant similarities in lip prints between monozygotic twins as opposed to unrelated individuals [9]

Despite genetic similarities, a sizable portion of twins (16.7%) in our study showed distinct lip print patterns, indicating that cheiloscopy patterns are not entirely the same even among twins. According to research conducted in Indian population by Koneru *et al.* (2013), Randhawa *et al.* (2011), and de Melo Soares *et al.* (2023) [5,7,14], simple vertical and branched groove patterns predominate. We observed low frequency of Type V patterns which adds credence to earlier research indicating that irregular patterns are comparatively uncommon and have a restricted prevalence among groups.

Our study has important forensic ramifications. Even among genetically identical individuals, cheiloscopy can help with individual differentiation, as seen by the occurrence of quadrant-level dissimilarities despite the

great degree of resemblance between twins. However, the 28% unmatched rate highlights quadrant-specific variations, possibly due to developmental or environmental factors, reinforcing cheiloscopy's value for distinguishing even twins in identification.^[14]

Vahanwala S *et.al* (2012), Okoh PD *et.al* (2019),^[11,15] in their studies found, even in identical twins, according to the study's conclusion that identical twins have similar but distinct lip prints, showing strong hereditary influence coupled with individual variances.

According to studies by Prabhu RV *et.al* (2013), Kolay SK *et.al* (2024) the use of advanced techniques such as digital photographic or intraoral scanners enhances the accuracy and reliability of collecting and comparing cheiloscopic patterns.^[16&17]

As lip prints are akin to fingerprints, remaining unchanged throughout an individual's life. These unique and reasonably stable patterns Sapasetty S *et.al* (2023)^[18] have been studied across different ethnicities, individuals, involving dactyloscopy, cheiloscopy, and rugoscopy among individuals with different skeletal malocclusion helping for individual identification during natural disaster.

Sutthiboonyapan P *et.al* (2025)^[19] study came to conclusion, as a result of lack of dangerous ingredients, and advantageous qualities including moisturizing and healing powers, herbal lipsticks are seen to be a safer option than traditional lip cosmetics. Their use is further supported by their biocompatibility and eco-friendliness, especially in research involving human subjects.

Deeper genetic insights may have been obtained; however, the number of samples was restricted to 25 twin pairs and zygosity (monozygotic versus dizygotic) was not differentiated. Furthermore, there was no longitudinal evaluation of lip print stability over time. To increase cheiloscopy's evidentiary value in forensic science, future research with bigger sample sizes, zygosity categorization, digital image processing, and multicentric populations is advised.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, this research provides important new information about the genetic foundation, variability, and forensic uses of cheiloscopic patterns in twins from Maharashtra. The results highlight their potential validity as indicators in forensic odontology, as well as their genetic determinism and individual individuality. The use of an herbal lip tint proved to be safe, acceptable, and effective for recording lip prints, indicating its potential as an alternative to conventional synthetic lipsticks.

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Conflicts of Interest:

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement:

The authors have decided to make the data available if necessary.

Authorship Statement:

Authors 1,2 and 3; *Dr. Viprada Pawar, Dr. Chetan Bhadage, Dr. Ajay Bhoosreddy* contributed to the conception and design of the study, conducted the literature search, handled data acquisition, performed data analysis, Author 4,5; *Dr. Saylee Kankal, Dr. Durga Varma* conducted statistical analysis, contributed to manuscript preparation, provided manuscript review, was involved in manuscript editing and is the guarantor of the study.

Abbreviations:

UR – Upper Right Quadrant, UL – Upper Left Quadrant, LR – Lower Right Quadrant, LL – Lower Left Quadrant, OPD – Outpatient Department, SPSS – Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, IEC – Institutional Ethics Committee.

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